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LINGUISTIC STATUS OF LANGUAGE INTERNET COMMUNICATIONS

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Abstract:

In this article we study the linguistic status of Internet Communications formed in the present conditions of the information society, and such slang can be nominated as a national version of the meta-language that possesses a novel function of the language. This function overwhelms non-verbal participants of communication interactions regardless of their nationality and command of any language.

Key words: Internet communication, Internet discourse, meta-language, national language version that combines the function of language.

The Internet occupies one of the key positions in development of modern society. The advent of the Internet has changed not only the way of life of a person, but also his perception of reality. By volume stored information and the scale of its transmission the Internet ranks first among all previously known methods of information processing. The Internet is a new huge world in which it interact more than two billion people. This circumstance contributes to the formation of the Internet as a powerful linguistic factor, which has led to a significant expansion of the lexical composition of many languages in the late XX – early XXI century. Yale University scientists R. Schenk, M. Lebowitz and L. Birnbaum conducted research on the development, creation and programming analyzers whose task was to transform the original natural language expressions into some internal representation [1, p. 401].

During the approbation of the SAM, ELI, FRUMP programs, experiments were carried out, during which there was revealed that the SAM program is not able to process texts for the perception which it is not prepared. At the same time, "any new vocabulary unit, a new area of discourse or one that has not been encountered before syntactic construction often led the system into complete confusion" [1, p. 406]. Conversely, the FRUMP program coped with the task: having the ability to read quickly, FRUMP, when getting acquainted with the text, was able to highlight everything that is interesting to itself. However, something similar happens in the human mind with his unpreparedness for the perception and understanding of

phenomena that the individual has not previously encountered. To such new phenomena, in particular, It is possible to attribute the metalanguage of Internet communication,

In the process of forming a new natural language of Internet communication, its initial nomination was as follows: "weblanguage" - English; "red-idioma" - Spanish; "rets langage" French; "web language" - Russian. etc., since "web" is English, "red" is Spanish, and "rets" is French for "network". However, today this is how a programming language is nominated, i.e. It is a purely technical term that is used to refer to artificially created sign systems designed to record computer programs.

In our study, we gave a name to the new natural language of Internet communication - metalanguage. In the Large Linguistic Dictionary "Linguistics" edited by V. N. Yartseva, we find the following definition of metalanguage.

“Metalanguage (from the Greek meta - through, after) is a language of the “second order”, in relation to which natural human language acts as a language - an object of linguistic research. The term "metalanguage" originally arose in mathematics and logic in the meaning: a formalized language, by means of which the properties of the corresponding subject (or object) theories are studied, the level of the described objects themselves and the level of their description are distinguished. Metalanguage is the subject of study of metalinguistics (the science of “second order” languages)” [2, p. 297].

In the dictionary of linguistic terms, O. S. Akhmanova also proposes a definition of metalanguage as a language of the “second order” (language-object); a language whose object is the content and expression of another language (in the second sense) [3, p. 323].

In the Encyclopedic Dictionary, the definition of metalanguage is as follows: “This is a language by means of which a description of the structural, deductive or semantic properties of some other (usually formalized language) is carried out, which is the subject of study of the corresponding metatheory” [4, With. 805].

Continuing to search for a definition of metalanguage on the Internet, we find interpretations that are essentially the same as the definitions given above. For example: “Metalanguage is a language by means of which the properties of some other language are described and studied – the so-called subject (object) language, or the language of an object” [5].

Another example: "Language is one of the most important concepts of modern logic, mathematics, philosophy and methodology of science, semiotics and theoretical linguistics. In the most general sense, a metalanguage is any natural or artificial language (the language of the "second level"), which describes another language (the language of the "first level"), which serves to describe the objects, properties and situation of the surrounding world or certain of its areas or spheres" [6]. From all the definitions given above, it follows that the metalanguage is considered only as the language of the "second plan", the purpose of which is to investigate the "language-object", namely, the natural human language.

At the same time, "metá" in Greek means "between, after, then"[6], which gives us every reason to reconsider the meaning of the word "meta-language" for linguistic science in the present conditions of the development of world civilization. The process of the birth of this language took place after there were already formed the natural languages of the human communication and exists between these languages, having managed find your niche. At the same time, it is in a state continuous interaction with them, becomes the "first-level" object language used when studying previously formed natural languages, which, in turn, are given the role of languages of the "second level", and vice versa. In other words, the metalanguage of the information space exists in two abstractions: as a second-level language and as a language capable of performing the function of a first-plan metalanguage, namely, it can be used to study the meta-language options that exist in the information space. Thus, in relation to this study, the term metalanguage is used by us as a new natural human language, born and existing in virtual reality and real space, actively interacting with other natural human languages with mutual influence and enrichment, and having the main functions inherent in natural language: communicative, emotive, voluntarily, representative and contact-establishing. It is also important for us to give a definition of a "variant" of a language, since in the future we will rely on the concept of a "variant of a metalanguage". We settled on the definition proposed in the dictionary of sociolinguistic terms: "A variant of a language (variety of a language) is a form of existence of a language, which is a modification of an invariant, which is 1) the system and structure of the language or 2) the norm of the language.

A variant of a language arises as a result of language differentiation under the influence of various extra linguistic factors. It is necessary to distinguish between a

variant of a language and speech varieties (individual, literary styles), although the opposition between linguistic and speech variability is not strict.[6, p. 35]. In connection with the above, it seems appropriate to give a definition of "variation in language ". The dictionary of sociolinguistic terms gives the following definition: "Language/speech variability is the ability of a language in the process of evolution to create competing means of expression at all levels (phonetic, morphemic, lexical, syntactic, stylistic) under the influence of internal patterns of language development or external causes.

Systemically organized sets of variable elements of the language are manifested in the differentiation of the idiom, i.e. in the emergence of various forms of language existence (in the broad sense). On the other hand, the variability of the language is manifested in the use of individual variable elements, due to the situation of communication or the social status of the communicants. If we consider Internet communication as momentary individual speech acts of communicants, we can characterize network interaction as manifestations of written speech. In this regard, it is expedient to propose a definition of internet-discourse.

Internet discourse is speech, verbal communication, coherent text, in conjunction with pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological and other factors, forming and functioning in a global system of interconnected computer networks, connecting users of both computer networks and individual computers, and enabling each user to exchange various information with another user and gain access to practically unlimited information resources. At the same time, it should be noted that the Internet discourse, being a verbal communication in the Internet environment, is served by a special language formed by natural in a way that has never before existed, because there was no computer-mediated interaction on the Internet before. Over the years of the existence of the Internet in the global network, its own speech norm has developed - a language system that is both a product of speech activity on the Internet and a new type of speech activity on the Web, i.e. language (speech activity = language + speech). This new language has its own patterns and rules at the lexical, phonological-graphic and grammatical levels.

Another concept that often characterizes the language of the Internet is this. "slang". Slang is a set of special words or new meanings already existing words used in various human associations, as well as the vocabulary of wide use for informal

communication. Moreover, in modern lexicography the second meaning prevails over the first. Indeed, at the beginning of its development, the language of the global network was a computer slang (jargon) used in mainly by professional computer users. As the Web developed and new means of network communication emerged, new varieties of slang appeared, which were used by a wider audience of users. Today, the language of Internet communication serves not only informal (ordinary, relaxed) communication, but also formal (business). Through this language, interaction on the Web becomes less formal, which contributes to more comfortable communication between social groups. At the level of the network language, today you can distinguish a lot of slang and jargon. Their conditions use, as a rule, can be determined by the following criteria:

- place of use (chat rooms, forums, games and etc.);
- the degree of formality – informality of the general

There are about two billion Internet users in the world today. Despite the linguistic boundaries, the linguistic and paralinguistic means available in the Internet discourse allow speakers of different national languages to understand each other, even when the participants in the conversation do not have a common language for communication. The monopolistic position of computer companies, most of which belong to the United States, has led to the active popularization of the English language. Today English is the language of new technologies and scientific achievements. At present, knowledge of the English language is perceived as a necessity, the English language is essentially becoming the business language of the entire earthly civilization. In other words, is English becoming one of the main components of the “intellect”? The answer to this question may be received in the future, but today we propose a definition of the language of communication on the Web as a metalanguage of Internet communication, which in each specific toponymic case can be considered as a national variant of the language.

As a result, we come to the conclusion that the metalanguage of Internet communication can be assigned the status of a national variant metalanguage of Internet communication, which has a new function of language in the modern conditions of the information society - uniting at the level of non-verbal interaction, since the formed non-verbal language of communication on the Web can be understood by all participants in communication, regardless of their nationality and knowledge of a particular language. Thus, in our opinion, in the modern environment of

communication, namely on the Internet, a new metalanguage has naturally developed, the analogues of which have not existed until today.

References

1.National Coalition for Dialogue & Deliberation // Engagement Streams Framework. 2014. Retrieved from http://www.ncdd.org/files/rc/2014_Engagement_Streams_Guide_Web.pdf

2.Volodenkov S.V. 2018. Mass communication and public consciousness in conditions of modern technological transformations // Magazine of political investigations. V. 2. Rel. 3, 1--8.

3.Filatova O., Misnikov Yu., Kbanov Yu. 2019. Public Deliberation in Russia: Deliberative Quality, Rationality an Interactivity of the Online Media Discussions // Media and Communication, V.7, Issue 3, 133--144.

4.Kalampokis E., Tambouris E., Tarabanis K.A. 2008. A domain model for eParticipation // Mellouk, A., Bi, J., Ortiz, G., et al. (eds) Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Internet and Web Application

5.Macintosh A. 2006. eParticipation in policy-making. The research and the challenges, exploiting the knowledge economy: issues, applications,

6.Medaglia R. 2007. Measuring the diffusion of eParticipation: A surveyon Italian local government. Information Polity, No 12 (4), 265